

Which Problems Are the Hardest? Who is the Best?
Analysis of Mathematical Ranking Methods in
Mathematical Olympiads

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Abstract

This paper uses Colley, Massey, and Elo ranking methods to rank problems and students on Math Olympiads. This paper analyzes the results of students in the three most challenging Math Olympiads in Kazakhstan: the National Math Olympiad, the Silk Road Math Competition, and the Asian-Pacific Math Olympiad, over three years: 2022, 2023, and 2024. We have expressed an Olympiad as an incomplete round-robin game where students play against the problems. Based on the results, we have fitted the data into the complex mathematical ranking methods of Colley, Massey, and Elo. Analysis has shown that we can identify which problems are hard to solve fully, but easy to get partial points on. Thus, coaches can use these results to categorize problems: which problems can be used to develop the skill of fully solving problems, and which problems help learners learn to earn partial points. Additionally, we have ranked the students and identified an innovative approach to ranking them based on their ability to earn points and their ability to fully solve the problem. Students and teachers can use these results to focus on the preparation of specific aspects of students' skills. Next, we have found that Elo can't be used to rank the problems and students, and identified a method to make Elo a reliable ranking method. Finally, we have discussed the unique application of Elo in problem ranking.

1 Introduction

Kazakhstani students participate in 4-6 national and international math Olympiads each year. Additionally, there are 30+ regional Olympiads. Over 3000 high school students try to advance to the final stages. Approximately 200 students are selected, and they compete with each other in the finals. Approximately 10% win gold, 15% win silver, and 20% win bronze medals during the finals.

This research paper focuses on deriving a method to analyze the data from previous Olympiads to derive rankings of problems and students based on these results. More specifically, this work aims to find out what problems are hard to get points on and what problems are hard to solve fully. Additionally, we have developed a method to rank students based on their ability to fully solve the problem and on their ability to earn partial points.

Consequently, these rankings may have four significant applications. First, identifying which problems are hard to solve fully, but easy to get partial points on, will allow coaches and students to select problems that will help to develop the skill of getting partial points. Additionally, students and coaches will have a rank of problems based on difficulty to solve, which is important because during self-study sessions and preparation camps, students tend to fully solve the problem, and not aim to get partial points. Next, the rankings of the students shown in this paper may be used by coaches and students to analyze their weak sides and focus on the development of specific skills. Lastly, these results may be used by the general public to see the rankings of students and problems.

This research plans to see an Olympiad as a game in which students play against problems. A participant can earn 0-7 points on each problem.

At first glance, it is possible to calculate the ranking by looking at the ratio

$$\frac{(\text{Number of students who have solved the problem})}{(\text{Number of participants})}.$$

However, in this case, a top student (the one who won gold last year, for example) and a mediocre student have the same impact on how complex the problem is. Sometimes, the problem is simple, but because it is placed as problem #6 (supposed to be the most complex), many students do not try to solve it. However, some students with low ratings may figure out the solution, which indicates that the problem is not so difficult.

Similar incidents appear frequently at the Olympiads. Therefore, the complexity of the problem should depend on the participant level. This paper investigates how to adjust Colley, Massey, and Elo ranking methods for this purpose. Work was also done on deriving rankings of the current students and predicting how they will perform in the upcoming Olympiads.

Overall, the field of math Olympiads is very popular, and there is a need for structured rankings of the problems for effective preparation. Additionally, individuals may want to use predictions of participants' performances to develop their skills. This research plans to use available data to derive a ranking of problems and students to achieve this by taking an Olympiad as a game where students play against problems. Afterward, this study investigates how ranking methods such as Colley, Massey, and Elo can be used to derive rankings that consider the participants' level and problems.

2 Related work

The Colley ranking method was developed by Dr. Wesley N. Colley and first introduced in his work “Colley’s bias free college football ranking method” [1]. In this paper, the researcher presents a ranking method that is implemented using computers. This method focuses only on the wins and losses of teams. Throughout the paper, the author shows how the methods work. By the end of the paper, he proves the following points about the Colley ranking method. 1. It has no bias toward conference, tradition, history, or prognostication. 2. It is reproducible; one can check the results. 3. It uses a minimum of assumptions. 4. It uses no ad hoc adjustments. 5. It nonetheless adjusts for the strength of schedule. 6. It ignores runaway scores. 7. It produces common-sense results that compare well to the press polls.

The Massey ranking method was developed by Kenneth Massey and described in “Statistical models applied to the rating of sports teams” [2]. The author describes how he uses mathematical techniques to create a rating system. At the end of the paper, the researcher shows an application to college football.

The Elo ranking method was developed by Arpad Elo and became immensely popular around the world. The most popular application of the Elo ranking method is in chess. The method was described in “The proposed USCF rating system, its development, theory, and applications” [3]. Unlike the previous two methods, Elo uses more statistics than linear algebra.

These methods were used before to analyze sports competitions. Still, some researchers adapted ranking methods for intellectual competitions. In [4], researchers analyze the results of countries participating in the International Informatics Olympiad to gain insights for coaches and identify successful years of performance by Egypt. They use Bayesian models-Elo, TrueSkill, and TopCoder-to achieve these purposes. Authors found the reliability of these ranking methods in ranking the competitions and compared them based on predictive accuracy.

Another study uses Deep Neural Networks to predict the rankings of countries in the International Math Olympiad 2020. [5]

3 Data and Methodology

3.1 Datasets

This paper analyzes the results of the students from three competitions: the National Math Olympiad, the Asian Pacific Math Olympiad (APMO), and the Silk Road Math Competition(SRMC). These three Olympiads are the hardest and most competitive Olympiads held in Kazakhstan: students must be the best in their region to qualify. These three Olympiads are used to identify the best students who will represent Kazakhstan at the International Math Olympiad.

Each Olympiad consists of 6, 5, and 4 problems, respectively. Each student can earn from 0 to 7 points on each of the problems, and the result of the student on the Olympiad is the sum of his points on each of the problems. A student gets 7 points for solving the problem, and 0 points if no progress is made. Partial points are given if the student has made

important progress in his work but could not solve the problem. Similarly, points may be deducted if a student has solved the problem, but there are minor mistakes in the student’s solution.

The dataset consists of students from grades 10-11 (12) who have earned non-zero points on the National Olympiad of the respective year. Students in grades 10 and 11 have the same problems, but students from grade 9 have easier ones. Therefore, we have excluded them from the dataset.

It is worth noting that students who have qualified for APMO and SRCM but did not qualify for the National Olympiad achieved low points; therefore, their performance had a negligible effect on the results, and we have excluded them as well for clarity.

Data was taken from the website *matol.kz* [6], which contains the results of the students on these three Olympiads in 2022, 2023, and 2024.

The data was then scraped as a game in which the students played against the problems. Let p be the score of the student on a particular problem. The following distribution was selected:

- $p \leq 2$: the student loses. Often, students can find the first steps, but they have made some progress and are not close to solving the problem. The student is awarded 0 points, and the problem earns $3 - p$ points.
- $3 \leq p \leq 4$: the student and the problem have a draw. Three or four points are most often given for considerable progress, and the student is close to solving a problem, but there are still important things that the student has to figure out. Student and problem is awarded 1 point each.
- $5 \leq p \leq 7$: the student wins. Usually, this happens when a student has solved the problem but made a minor mistake that is easy to fix. The student is awarded $p - 4$ points, and the problem gets 0 points.

3.2 Rating systems

This section shows how Colley, Massey, and Elo ranking methods were used for ranking the students and the problems. The work and advantages of the Colley and the Massey methods were described in “Sports ranking with nonuniform weighting” [7]. The concept of work of Elo is covered in “Rating the chess rating system” [8]. Here is a brief explanation of how methods are used in the ranking of students and problems.

3.2.1 Colley

To find the ratings of students and problems, we express them as a partial round-robin tournament. Both problems and students are represented as players, and there are games between students and problems only.

We create a square Colley Matrix C with length equal to the number of teams. The diagonal elements of the C are $2 + t_i$, where t_i is the total number of games played by player i , and the off-diagonal elements c_{ij} , for $i \neq j$, are $-n_{ij}$, where n_{ij} is the number of games between teams i and j . Also let b be $n \times 1$ vector that has components $b_i = 1 + \frac{1}{2}(w_i - l_i)$,

where w_i is the number of wins, and l_i is the number of losses by the player i . To find the Colley ranking, we solve the following equation:

$$Cr = b,$$

and the solution vector r will be our Colley ranking for the teams.

Example. Suppose students A, B, C have competed in a tournament with problems numbered 1, 2, 3. The results are shown in Table 1.

Student	P1	P2	P3
A	7	7	6
B	7	5	2
C	6	1	0

Table 1: Results of the Olympiad

Based on these results, we will create a Colley matrix using the rules for point distribution from section 3 and rules to create a matrix from above. We will get the following Table 2:

Players	A	B	C	P1	P2	P3
A	5	0	0	-1	-1	-1
B	0	5	0	-1	-1	-1
C	0	0	5	-1	-1	-1
P1	-1	-1	-1	5	0	0
P2	-1	-1	-1	0	5	0
P3	-1	-1	-1	0	0	5

Table 2: Colley Matrix for the Olympiad

We can see that each student has played exactly once against each of the problems, and each problem has played exactly once against each of the students. Next, we create matrix b :

A	2.5
B	1.5
C	0.5
P1	-0.5
P2	0.5
P3	1.5

Table 3: b matrix for the Olympiad

Lastly, we find the solution to the equation and find the Colley ratings of both players

and students.

$$\begin{pmatrix} 5 & 0 & 0 & -1 & -1 & -1 \\ 0 & 5 & 0 & -1 & -1 & -1 \\ 0 & 0 & 5 & -1 & -1 & -1 \\ -1 & -1 & -1 & 5 & 0 & 0 \\ -1 & -1 & -1 & 0 & 5 & 0 \\ -1 & -1 & -1 & 0 & 0 & 5 \end{pmatrix} \cdot r = \begin{pmatrix} 2.5 \\ 1.5 \\ 0.5 \\ -0.5 \\ 0.5 \\ 1.5 \end{pmatrix}$$

Solving this equation, we get:

$$r = \begin{pmatrix} 0.7625 \\ 0.5625 \\ 0.3625 \\ 0.2375 \\ 0.4375 \\ 0.6375 \end{pmatrix}$$

Thus, ratings of both students and problems can be shown in Table 4 and Table 5.

A	0.7625
B	0.5625
c	0.3625

Table 4: Rating of Students Sorted

P3	0.6375
P2	0.4375
P1	0.2375

Table 5: Rating of Problems Sorted

Similarly, we find ratings of students and problems further in this paper.

3.2.2 Massey

The Massey ranking uses similar linear algebra methods to derive ratings of the players. Its difference is that it also accounts for the difference in points in the games. In general, if Team A beats Team B by 3 points, and Team B beats Team C by 2 points, Massey predicts that A will beat C by 5 points. In the context of a math Olympiad, a student who got 7 points on a problem would be ranked higher than a student who got 6 points, even though they both won against the problem.

More about the Massey method can be read in “Sports ranking with nonuniform weighting” [7]. To find the ratings using this system, we create a Massey matrix M , same as in Colley method (Section 3.2.1): each diagonal element equals the number of games played by the corresponding team, and each off-diagonal element equals $-g$, where g is the number of times the corresponding teams played. However, RHS matrix b will be the sum of the point differentials, where a win gives a positive differential and a loss gives a negative one. Lastly,

we replace any row with 1's and the RHS with 0 to get a system of equations with solutions. Our ratings could be derived by solving the equation

$$M \cdot r = b.$$

Example. Consider the same Olympiad that was given in Section 3.2.1.

Student	P1	P2	P3
<i>A</i>	7	7	6
<i>B</i>	7	5	2
<i>C</i>	6	1	0

Table 6: Results of the Olympiad

From these results, we built the Massey matrix M as shown in Table 7.

Players	<i>A</i>	<i>B</i>	<i>C</i>	P1	P2	P3
<i>A</i>	5	0	0	-1	-1	-1
<i>B</i>	0	5	0	-1	-1	-1
<i>C</i>	0	0	5	-1	-1	-1
P1	-1	-1	-1	5	0	0
P2	-1	-1	-1	0	5	0
P3	-1	-1	-1	0	0	5

Table 7: Massey Matrix for the Olympiad

Calculating the RHS, we get the matrix b as shown in Table 8. It is worth noting that point differentials when building a b matrix are not direct, but as defined in Section 3.

<i>A</i>	$3+3+2=8$
<i>B</i>	$3+1-1=3$
<i>C</i>	$2-2-3=-3$
P1	$-3-3-2=-8$
P2	$-3-1+2=-2$
P3	$-2+1+3=2$

Table 8: b matrix for the Olympiad

Lastly, we find the solution to the equation and find the Colley ratings of both players and students.

$$\begin{pmatrix} 5 & 0 & 0 & -1 & -1 & -1 \\ 0 & 5 & 0 & -1 & -1 & -1 \\ 0 & 0 & 5 & -1 & -1 & -1 \\ -1 & -1 & -1 & 5 & 0 & 0 \\ -1 & -1 & -1 & 0 & 5 & 0 \\ 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \cdot r = \begin{pmatrix} 8 \\ 3 \\ -3 \\ -8 \\ -2 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix}$$

Solving this equation, we get:

$$r = \begin{pmatrix} 1.4 \\ 0.4 \\ -0.8 \\ -1.4 \\ -0.2 \\ 0.6 \end{pmatrix}$$

Thus, ratings of both students and problems can be shown in Table 9 and Table 10.

A	1.4
B	0.4
c	-0.8

Table 9: Rating of Students Sorted

P3	0.6
P2	-0.2
P1	-1.4

Table 10: Rating of Problems Sorted

Similarly, we find ratings of students and problems further in this paper.

3.2.3 Elo

In Elo, the difference in the ratings between two players serves as a predictor of the outcome of a match. After every game, the winning player takes points from the losing one. The difference between the ratings of the winner and loser determines the total number of points gained or lost after a game. Note that Elo ratings change over the season. In Elo, we assume that a player's performance in each game is normally distributed. The mean value of the performances of any given player changes only slowly over time. A player's true skill = the mean of that player's performance random variable.

Assume R_A = rating for player A and R_B = rating for player B .

The expected score of Player A is

$$E_A = \frac{1}{1 + 10^{(R_B - R_A)/400}}$$

The expected score of Player B is

$$E_B = \frac{1}{1 + 10^{(R_A - R_B)/400}}$$

Suppose that player A is expected to score E_A but scores S_A when playing player B .

Then, player A 's rating is updated as

$$R'_A = R_A + K(S_A - E_A)$$

The expected score of Player B is

$$E_B = \frac{1}{1 + 10^{(R_A - R_B)/400}}$$

3.2.4 Tuning K

The usual factor K , used in chess, is 32. Too small a value of K will result in slow rating updates; therefore, ratings will not reflect the recent developments. On the contrary, a very high K will make recent developments too important. Below, we searched for the optimal K .

For Elo, we can convert a rating into a probability of winning. Let p_{ij} , be the probability of team i winning a game against team j . For any game, we are interested in the square error:

$$(p_{ij} - o_{ij})^2 - (p_{ji} - o_{ji})^2$$

where o_{ij} , is 1 if team i beats team j and 0 otherwise. Note that in the case of perfect prediction, when $p_{ij} = 1$, and $o_{ij} = 1$, we get a square error that is equal to 0. We want to minimize this square error. For our dataset in 2024, we check K from 24 to 1000 with a step size of 0.2 and get the best $K = 136$, as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Finding the Best K in 2024

We use a similar method later in the Section 4.1.2 to find K .

4 Analysis

In this section, we will compare different methods, their results on the ranking of problems, and their correlation with the sum of the points students earned on respective problems. We will then specifically analyze the results for Elo.

4.1 Problem rankings

Let us define a *PointSum* for a problem as the sum of points students got on that problem. In Figures 2, 3, and 4, we can see each problem, its rank among players (students and problems), its rating, and *PointSum* of this respective problem. In further sections, we look at these results to describe the findings of this research.

MASSEY-2024 - RANKED			
Problem	Rank	Rating	PointSum
A_4	1	2.751183	2
S_4	2	2.751183	2
A_3	3	2.705206	7
N_3	4	2.590264	18
A_5	5	2.590264	18
S_3	6	2.406356	36
N_6	8	2.073022	67
N_5	9	2.015551	76
N_2	11	1.969574	83
A_2	19	1.084517	170
S_2	30	0.601758	215
S_1	37	0.406356	238
A_1	69	-0.835024	366
N_4	88	-1.2833	414
N_1	102	-2.179851	502

(a) Massey 2024

COLLEY-2024-RANKED			
Problem	Rank	Rating	PointSum
A_4	1	0.950897	2
S_4	2	0.950897	2
A_3	3	0.939661	7
N_3	4	0.928425	18
A_5	5	0.928425	18
S_3	6	0.889099	36
N_6	7	0.883481	67
N_5	8	0.838537	76
N_2	9	0.821683	83
A_2	19	0.686852	170
S_2	21	0.658762	215
S_1	30	0.591346	238
A_1	77	0.366627	366
N_4	97	0.276739	414
N_1	102	0.158762	502

(b) Colley 2024

ELO-2024-RANKED			
Problem	Rank	Rating	PointSum
N_3	1	716.717328	18
A_4	2	681.920843	2
N_6	3	668.637071	67
A_3	4	654.882928	7
A_5	5	652.624955	18
S_4	6	651.516135	2
S_3	7	609.644169	36
N_2	8	608.632112	83
N_5	9	588.110598	76
S_2	10	511.834737	215
S_1	11	510.240253	238
A_2	12	501.733437	170
A_1	13	455.267412	366
N_4	14	239.526638	502
N_4	15	176.779641	414

(c) Elo 2024

POINTSUM-2024-RANKED	
Problem	PointSum
A_4	2
S_4	2
A_3	7
N_3	18
A_5	18
S_3	36
N_6	67
N_5	76
N_2	83
A_2	170
S_2	215
S_1	238
A_1	366
N_4	414
N_1	502

(d) PointSum 2024

Figure 2: Different Ranking Methods for 2024

MASSEY - 2023 - RANKED			
Problem	Rank	Rating	PointSum
A_5	1	2.647505	0
N_4	2	2.622814	2
N_6	3	2.622814	2
N_3	5	2.511703	12
S_4	6	2.499357	14
N_5	7	2.28949	34
S_3	8	2.277135	34
A_4	10	2.203061	39
A_1	11	2.00553	62
A_2	13	1.943801	65
A_3	14	1.906764	66
N_2	15	1.882073	70
S_2	17	1.672197	90
S_1	18	1.277135	129
N_1	96	-1.809285	417

(a) Massey 2023

COLLEY - 2023 - RANKED			
Problem	Rank	Rating	PointSum
N_4	1	0.929493	2
N_6	2	0.929493	2
A_5	3	0.929493	0
N_3	4	0.917445	12
S_4	5	0.905397	14
A_4	6	0.893349	39
N_5	7	0.875277	34
S_3	8	0.875277	34
A_3	10	0.863228	66
A_2	11	0.833108	65
A_1	12	0.82106	62
N_2	13	0.815036	70
S_2	15	0.796963	90
S_1	18	0.712626	129
N_1	96	0.254795	417

(b) Colley 2023

ELO - 2023 - RANKED			
Problem	Rank	Rating	PointSum
N_3	1	701.849299	12
N_4	2	698.112568	2
N_6	3	681.792023	2
N_5	4	653.072033	34
A_5	5	648.576556	0
N_2	6	640.60879	70
A_4	7	629.85622	39
A_1	8	623.719236	62
S_4	9	605.631987	14
A_3	10	596.964661	66
S_3	11	580.297675	34
S_2	12	583.987122	90
A_2	13	581.835276	65
S_1	14	565.465465	129
N_1	15	446.546662	417

(c) Elo 2023

POINTSUM - 2023 - RANKED	
Problem	PointSum
A_5	0
N_4	2
N_6	2
N_3	12
S_4	14
N_5	34
S_3	34
A_4	39
A_1	62
A_2	65
A_3	66
N_2	70
S_2	90
S_1	129
N_1	417

(d) PointSum 2023

Figure 3: Different Ranking Methods for 2023

Figure 4: Different Ranking Methods for 2022

4.1.1 What Colley and Massey tell us?

We can see that Colley and Massey’s methods correlate with *PointSum*. The lower the rating, the more points students were able to get from that specific problem. On the contrary, the Elo ranking method is consistently unrelated to *PointSum*. For example, problem *A5* is ranked #5, even though no one was able to get even a single point on it. This behaviour of Elo is discussed further in Section 4.1.2.

In all three years, we can see that Massey correlates mostly ideally with *PointSum*. Only two special occasions happened in 2023, Figure 3a, when *N5* and *S3* had the same *PointSum*, but slightly different ratings; and in 2022, Figure 4a, when *S2* and *N2* had different ratings but the same sum of the points. Still, the difference in ratings is negligible. While Colley correlates ideally with *PointSum* in 2024, there are some significant disorders in 2023 and 2022.

Case Study: Why is *A3* harder than *A1*?

In 2023, Figure 3b, *A3* has a sum of the points equal to 66, and *A1* has a *PointSum* of 62. Logically, the problem with 62 points must be harder, because fewer students were able to get points on that problem. However, if we look at Colley ratings, *A3* is much harder. The rating difference is more than 0.04, which is relatively huge. For example, the *Pointsum* difference between problems *S4* and *A4* is 25, but the rating difference is slightly above 0.01. So, why does this happen, and, more importantly, what does it tell us?

Looking at the database, we can see the following:

- Problem *A1*: There are **5** students who got **5+** points (student wins), **4** students who got **3-4 points** (draw), and **0** students who got **1-2** points (student loses)
- Problem *A3*: There are **5** students who got **5+** points (student wins), **1** student who got **3-4** points (draw), and **13(!)** students who got **1-2** points (student loses).

Thus, we can see that while more points were earned by students in problem *A3*, a lot of students have made insignificant progress and earned only 1-2 points. On the other hand, all students who have earned points in *A1* must have made major progress in the solution of the problem. Therefore, *A3* is harder to solve than *A1*. Let’s look at another example from 2022 (Figure 4b):

Problem	<i>N2</i>	<i>A3</i>
PointSum	123	112
Rank	8	9
Rating	0.78	0.73
Students with 5+ points	13	14
Students with 3-4 points	1	7
Students with 1-2 points	27	6

Table 11: *N2* vs *A3* in 2022

We can again see that significantly more students have made little progress in *N2*, but fewer students were able to make considerable progress than in the problem *A3*. Comparing other problems that do not correlate with *PointSum* produces similar results: we find that students made little progress in solving the problem.

So what?

Looking at the difference between the Colley, Massey, and *PointSum* methods gives us the opportunity to find interesting insight about the Math Olympiad problems that would not be obvious otherwise: we can identify which problems are hard to solve, but easy to earn points on. This finding is crucial and innovative because it allows Olympiad coaches and students who are self-studying to identify problems that are good to make partial progress in. Sometimes problems are hard to solve fully; therefore, coaches aim to train students to get at least some points. Such problems can be identified using the Colley method. Moreover, Colley’s method shows how hard the problem is, while Massey shows how overall it is hard to get points on the problem.

4.1.2 Elo analysis

In Section 4.1.1, we have analyzed the behaviour of the Colley and Massey methods. Both of them more or less correlate with *PointSum*. Elo, on the contrary, doesn’t correlate with the sum of the points at all. For example, in 2024, *S4* is ranked #6 with *PointSum* 2, while *N6* is ranked #3 with *PointSum* 67. We can see the rankings of the problems and predictability of methods in Figure 5.

PROBLEM RANKINGS 2024				
	Massey	Colley	Elo	PointSum
A_4	1	1	2	1
S_4	2	2	6	2
A_3	3	3	4	3
N_3	4	4	1	4
A_5	5	5	5	5
S_3	6	6	7	6
N_6	7	7	3	7
N_5	8	8	9	8
N_2	9	9	8	9
A_2	10	10	12	10
S_2	11	11	10	11
S_1	12	12	11	12
A_1	13	13	13	13
N_4	14	14	15	14
N_1	15	15	14	15
Predictability	89.35%	88.12%	87.36%	

Figure 5: All Methods 2024 Compared

Despite the fact that the ranking of the problems in Elo differs significantly, the predictability of the method is still high — 87.36%. In Figure 2c, we can see that all of the problems are ranked higher than the students; it means that theoretically, any problem beats any student. Students can get $7 * 15 * 88 = 9240$ if each of the 88 students solves each of 15 problems correctly and earns 7 points. However, the sum of points is equal to 2214, which is 23%. This may be one of the possible explanations for the high predictability of Elo. Still, the rankings of the problems are incorrect. Note that Colley’s and Massey’s methods use linear algebra, and the order of the games doesn’t matter. Elo, on the contrary, continuously updates its ratings. Therefore, the possible reason for such incorrect rankings may be the order of the games. In the initial dataset, games were sorted from the strongest student to the weakest. Further, we have scrambled students in random order 5 times and looked at the results.

Looking at the scrambled data.

For each scrambled dataset, we have calculated the best K value, which is indicated at the heading of each table. By looking at results in Figure 6, we can see that scrambled Elo correlates much better than sorted Elo. Therefore, despite taking into account the order of the games, when randomly scrambling the data, Elo still can be a good indicator of how hard the problem is. Another finding is that K is always comparatively big. Usually, the K value is about 30.

ELO-scrambled random 1-157.6- sorted				
Problem	Rank	Rating	PointSum	
S_4	1	868.86308	2	
A_3	2	841.708459	7	
A_4	3	833.234293	2	
A_5	4	744.327194	18	
S_3	5	584.915524	36	
N_3	6	518.434253	18	
N_5	7	481.661931	76	
N_6	8	478.411738	67	
N_2	18	308.477855	83	
S_2	25	161.764958	215	
S_1	26	130.489061	238	
A_2	28	109.809972	170	
N_1	75	-200.614458	502	
N_4	85	-268.487757	414	
A_1	95	-300.06936	366	

ELO-scrambled random 2 164.4- sorted				
Problem	Rank	Rating	PointSum	
S_4	1	872.201381	2	
A_4	2	830.844237	2	
A_3	3	716.133894	7	
N_3	4	708.138883	18	
S_3	5	631.731022	36	
A_5	6	591.632834	18	
N_6	8	465.398508	67	
N_2	10	456.387703	83	
N_5	11	441.250647	76	
A_2	24	189.504301	170	
S_2	26	154.622762	215	
S_1	36	71.298075	238	
A_1	81	-255.376502	366	
N_1	93	-330.690175	502	
N_4	98	-373.331646	414	

ELO-scrambled random 3-151.6- sorted				
Problem	Rank	Rating	PointSum	
S_4	1	830.893745	2	
A_4	2	805.51531	2	
A_5	3	708.755728	18	
A_3	4	703.441594	7	
N_3	5	636.734036	18	
S_3	6	570.734237	36	
N_6	7	483.012041	67	
N_5	9	440.68469	76	
N_2	13	346.002842	83	
S_2	17	295.958887	215	
S_1	26	143.699977	238	
A_2	38	55.470834	170	
N_4	41	10.553226	414	
N_1	47	-43.876675	502	
A_1	49	-51.133304	366	

(a) Scramble 1

(b) Scramble 2

(c) Scramble 3

ELO-scrambled random 4-149.4- sorted				
Problem	Rank	Rating	PointSum	
S_4	1	834.028906	2	
A_4	2	805.790674	2	
A_3	3	687.000002	7	
S_3	4	684.353529	36	
A_5	5	580.057757	18	
N_3	6	567.394783	18	
N_5	7	515.277771	76	
N_2	10	389.118695	83	
N_6	11	379.110823	67	
A_2	20	274.78963	170	
S_2	21	272.426027	215	
S_1	29	137.449006	238	
A_1	35	66.686409	366	
N_4	67	-167.512388	414	
N_1	80	-232.343937	502	

(d) Scramble 4

ELO-scrambled random 5-143- sorted				
Problem	Rank	Rating	PointSum	
S_4	1	806.457177	2	
A_4	2	778.857774	2	
A_3	3	763.921515	7	
A_5	4	759.923395	18	
N_3	5	668.395473	18	
N_6	6	577.202242	67	
S_3	7	559.659823	36	
N_5	8	487.040373	76	
A_2	12	325.701258	170	
N_2	13	323.543089	83	
S_2	22	230.388973	215	
S_1	24	187.200261	238	
A_1	38	7.792038	366	
N_1	59	-116.070984	502	
N_4	80	-226.537543	414	

(e) Scramble 5

Figure 6: Different Ranking Methods for 2024

In Figure 7 we can see the comparison of Scrambled Elo to Colley, Massey, and *PointSum*. We can see from Figures 2a and 2b that *A4* and *S4* have the same rating. In scrambled Elo, however, we can see that *S4* always has a higher rating.

PROBLEM RANKINGS 2024										
	Scramble 1	Scramble 2	Scramble 3	Scramble 4	Scramble 5	Elo-ranked	PointSum	Massey	Colley	
A_4	3	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	1	1
S_4	1	1	1	1	1	6	2	2	2	2
A_3	2	3	4	3	3	4	7	3	3	3
N_3	6	4	5	6	5	1	18	4	4	4
A_5	4	6	3	5	4	5	18	5	5	5
S_3	5	5	6	4	7	7	36	6	6	6
N_6	8	7	7	9	6	3	67	7	7	7
N_5	7	9	8	7	8	9	76	8	8	8
N_2	9	8	9	8	10	8	83	9	9	9
A_2	12	10	12	10	9	12	170	10	10	10
S_2	10	11	10	11	11	10	215	11	11	11
S_1	11	12	11	12	12	11	238	12	12	12
A_1	15	13	15	13	13	13	366	13	13	13
N_4	14	15	13	14	15	15	414	14	14	14
N_1	13	14	14	15	14	14	502	15	15	15
K	157.60	164.40	151.6	149.4	143					

Figure 7: All Methods 2024 Compared+Scrambled Elo

Both *A4* and *S4* have *PointSum* of 2. We compared rankings of students who have earned points on these problems in Table 12.

Problem	<i>A4</i>	<i>S4</i>
Rank of Student #1 who earned a point	3	2
Rank of Student #2 who earned a point	7	43

Table 12: Students who earned points on *A4* and *S4*

We can see that *S4* should be ranked higher than *A4* because a much weaker student who is ranked #43 earned the point on the problem *S4*. Still, both problems are ranked equally in Colley and Massey. The reasons why Elo is more precise in this case than the Colley and Massey methods are grounds for further research.

4.2 Student Ranking

In our database, students and problems played against each other. In the section above, we have analyzed how Colley, Massey, and Elo methods rank problems. In this section, we analyze how these methods do student ranking. In Figure 8, we have plotted ranks in *Pointsum* against rank in Massey, Colley, and Elo methods, respectively. Additionally, we have calculated Spearman Rank Correlation Coefficient and Kendall’s Tau Coefficient to check if the methods correlate. We can see in Figure 8a that the Massey method has relatively high coefficients, and the ranks of *PointSum* and the Massey method correlate. The Colley method, as can be seen in Figure 8b, correlates with *PointSum*, but not as closely as the Massey method. Lastly, the Elo method doesn’t correlate at all and has relatively low Coefficient values, as can be seen in Figure 8c.

Figure 8: Student vs Method Correlation

As we have found earlier in Section 4.1, Massey is a good method for identifying which problems are hard to get points on, and Colley is a good method for ranking how hard it is to fully solve the problem. We can see that Colley is different from Massey and *PointSum* by looking at the Top 10 students who got promoted, and the Top 10 students who got demoted by the Colley Method in Tables 13, 14.

Name	PointSum	Colley Rating	Rank Score	Rank Colley	Rank Diff
Nurislam Aldabergenuly	13	0.374717	63	53	10
Timur Tsoy	5	0.315894	81	71	10
Beksultan Ortai	13	0.374717	63	55	8
Alimzhan Turdaly	14	0.374717	58	51	7
Nariman Abishev	7	0.315894	75	69	6
Akerke Nurakhmetova	18	0.433541	47	42	5
Adil Amirzhanov	23	0.433541	43	38	5
Alpamys Iskendir	28	0.492364	36	31	5
Danila Aksenov	14	0.374717	58	53	5
Alimargulan Amirtai	38	0.580600	23	19	4

Table 13: Top 10 students promoted by Colley

Name	PointSum	Colley Rating	Rank Score	Rank Colley	Rank Diff
Aldiyar Mazkenov	18	0.374717	47	61	-14
Zhanarys Tendikov	17	0.374717	50	61	-11
Ernur Tursyntai	15	0.374717	54	64	-10
Zhanibek Rasululy	15	0.374717	54	63	-9
Alikhan Babazhan	8	0.315894	73	81	-8
Serik Murzabek	42	0.580600	14	22	-8
Alikhan Bekbolatov	9	0.315894	70	77	-7
Erasyl Anuarbek	9	0.315894	70	77	-7
Beibarys Zhenisbek	25	0.433541	40	45	-5
Nuridin Qaysa	26	0.433541	39	44	-5

Table 14: Top 10 students demoted by Colley

Let’s look at two students: Aibyn and Adil. Aibyn is ranked #35 by *PointSum* with 29 points earned in total. Adil is ranked #43 with 23 points earned. However, according to the Colley method, Adil is ranked #38 and Aibyn is ranked #39. If we look at their results, we will see that Aibyn has solved problems *N1*, *N4*, and *A1*, and earned 2 points from the problems *N6*, *A2*, *A5*, and *S2*. Adil has solved problems *N1*, *N4*, and *S1*, and earned 1 point from the problems *S2* and *S4*. Since we look only at wins and losses at the Colley method, Adil indeed should be ranked higher, because from Figure 2b we can see that *S1* is harder than *A1*.

Thus, we have identified that the Massey method could be used to rank students based on their ability to get points, and the Colley method can be applied to rank students based on their ability to solve problems. These findings could be used by students and coaches who want to find students who can solve problems. Additionally, these findings could be used to identify the weak sides of students to prepare for. If a student has a higher Massey rank than Colley, then the student should improve their ability to fully solve the problem. If an olympiad participant got ranked higher in the Colley than in the Massey method, then it means that he should improve his ability to get partial points. Specific problems could be selected to achieve each of these purposes using the ranking of problems from Section 4.1.

5 Conclusion and Future Work

Overall, by looking at the results of students who have participated in Math Olympiads in the years 2022-2024, we were able to find several valuable insights in the field of ranking Olympiad problems. First, in Section 3 we have designed Math Olympiads as a game and adapted the ranking methods of Colley, Massey, and Elo to rank **both** problems and students. Next, in Section 4.1.1 we have closely analyzed how Massey and Colley correlate with *PointSum*. This paper describes an innovative approach to ranking problems, finding problems that are good to train on, making progress on, and identifying which problems are hard to solve fully and which problems are hard to earn points on. After, in Section 4.1.2 we have analyzed the behaviour of Elo and discovered that, when used with a scrambled dataset, Elo may be used to rank the problems. Moreover, we have found that Elo may be more accurate when ranking problems with equal *PointSum* than Colley and Massey.

Additionally, we have used the Colley and Massey methods to rank students who participated in the Olympiads, and have shown how these rankings correlate with original rankings.

In the future, more years and different Olympiads could be implemented. Additionally, the reasons behind the chaotic behaviour of Elo could be analysed. For example, if we look at Figure 3c, we can see that $A5$ is ranked #5, even though no one could earn a single point on this problem. Even if order matters, theoretically, a problem without losses should be ranked #1, because it always wins.

Looking at the problems as players, and creating a ranking over several years, could be a topic of another research as well. Then we can use Elo because games will be in order, each year.

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